

LITERACY RATE IN INDIA IN 2022

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ABSTRACT

The literacy rate in India in 2022 is examined in this research. An important factor in determining a country's degree of development is literacy. The percentage of adults over the age of fifteen who are literate is known as the literacy rate. Some emerging nations are attempting to raise the literacy rate, including Bangladesh, Nepal, Laos, and India. In the past ten years, India's literacy rate has increased significantly. India still has lower levels of literacy than many other nations, though. The literacy rate is 77.70%, with literate males at 84.70% and literate females at 70.30%, according to the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5) and National Statistical Office: NSO (2021 and 2022). Women appear to have a low literacy rate despite the high percentage of males that are literate.

KEYWORDS: *NFHS-5, NSO Data, Literacy Rate, India*

LITERATURE REVIEW:

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2. Female Literacy Rate is a Better Predictor of Birth Rate and Infant Mortality Rate in India [J Family Med Prim Care](#). 2013 Oct-Dec; 2(4): 349–353. DOI: [10.4103/2249-4863.123889](https://doi.org/10.4103/2249-4863.123889).
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OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To examine the literacy rate in India 2022.
 2. To identify the states with highest literacy rate in India 2022.
 3. To identify the states with lowest literacy rate in India 2022.
 4. To study the differences between male and female literacy rate in India.
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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

1. Secondary data: NSO literacy rate data for 2022, statistics gathered from NFHS-5.
2. The data from the national surveys conducted by the NFHS-5, NSO data on the literacy rate in India 2022, undergone an ecological analysis. State-by-state literacy rates were derived from the Indian Censuses of 2021 and 2022. To provide a precise percentage measure for consistent comparison, we chose literacy rates as a reflection of educational status.
3. The descriptive research approach.

INTRODUCTION:

An individual's ability to communicate through reading and writing is referred to as literacy. Any population's literacy rate calculates the proportion of people over a given age who are literate. The average literacy rate in India was 77.70% as of the year 2021, according to data from the National Statistical Office (NSO). In India, male literacy is at 84.70% and female literacy is currently 70.30% as of 2021.

According to the National Family Health Survey 2019–21 (NFHS-5), adult women (15–49 years) have a literacy rate of 71.5%, while adult men (15–49 years) have an 87.4% rate.

According to the 2011 Census, there are 763,498,517 (76.34 billion) literate people in the nation. Of these, 328,814,738 (32.88 Crore) are women and 434,683,779 (43.46 Crore) are men. While the nation's total literacy rate is 72.9%, the gender gap at the national level is 16.25 percentage points, with males having a literacy rate of 80.89% and females having a rate of 64.64%.

Variables	Literate Population 2011	Literacy Rate 2011	Literacy Rate 2021
Persons	763498517	72.99	77.70
Males	434683779	80.89	84.70
Females	328814738	64.64	70.30

Source: Census 2011 and 2022, National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5) & National Statistical Office (NSO) data 2022.

The percentage of people aged 7 and older who are literate is known as the literacy rate. Literacy is defined as the ability to read and write a simple message with understanding in any language.

List of States & Union Territories by Literacy Rate 2022:

Male literacy in India is expected to be 84.4% in 2021, while female literacy is expected to be 71.5%, according to the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5) 2019–21.

Male literacy is 84.7% over all of India, while female literacy is 70.3%, creating a gender difference of 12.9 percentage points. Kerala has the smallest gender literacy gap, with a difference of just 2.2 percentage points.

Kerala topped the list with 96.2%, while Andhra Pradesh had the lowest literacy rate of all the Indian states with 66.4%. In second place with 88.7% was Delhi. The list of States and Union territories with literacy rates may be seen below.

States & Union Territories	Male Literacy Rate %	Female Literacy Rate %	Average Literacy Rate %
A&N islands	90.11	81.84	86.27
Andhra Pradesh	73.4	59.5	66.4

Arunachal Pradesh	73.69	59.57	66.95
Assam	90.1	81.2	85.9
Bihar	79.7	60.5	70.9
Chhattisgarh	85.4	68.7	77.3
Chandigarh	90.54	81.38	86.43
Dadra and Nagar Haveli	86.46	65.93	77.65
Daman & Diu	91.48	79.59	87.07
Delhi	93.7	82.4	88.7
Goa	92.81	81.84	87.4
Gujarat	89.5	74.8	82.4
Haryana	88	71.3	80.4
Himachal Pradesh	92.9	80.5	86.6
Jammu & Kashmir	85.7	68	77.3
Jharkhand	83	64.7	74.3
Karnataka	83.4	70.5	77.2
Kerala	97.4	95.2	96.2
Lakshadweep	96.11	88.25	92.28
Madhya Pradesh	81.2	65.5	73.7
Maharashtra	90.7	78.4	84.8
Manipur	86.49	73.17	79.85
Meghalaya	77.17	73.78	75.48
Mizoram	93.72	89.4	91.58
Nagaland	83.29	76.69	80.11
Odisha	84	70.3	77.3
Puducherry	92.12	81.22	86.55
Punjab	88.5	78.5	83.7
Rajasthan	80.8	57.6	69.7
Sikkim	87.29	76.43	82.2
Tamil Nadu	87.9	77.9	82.9
Telangana	80.5	65.1	72.8
Tripura	92.18	83.15	87.75
Uttarakhand	94.3	80.7	87.6
Uttar Pradesh	81.8	63.4	73
West Bengal	84.8	76.1	80.5
All-India	84.7	70.3	77.7

Source: Survey by National Statistical Office (NSO). *UTs & NE States based on 2011 Census

Indian States with Highest Literacy Rate 2022: According to data from the National Statistical Office (NSO) for 2017–18 on the nation's states' overall literacy rates, Kerala came out on top with a score of 96.2%. In second place with 88.7% was Delhi.

States having the highest rate of literacy:

Sl. No.	State	Male	Female	Average
1	Kerala	97.4	95.2	96.2
2	Mizoram	93.72	89.4	91.58
3	Delhi	93.7	82.4	88.7
4	Tripura	92.18	83.15	87.75
5	Uttarakhand	94.3	80.7	87.6
6	Goa	92.81	81.84	87.4
7	Himachal Pradesh	92.9	80.5	86.6
8	Assam	90.1	81.2	85.9
9	Maharashtra	90.7	78.4	84.8
10	Punjab	88.5	78.5	83.7

*Source: survey by National Statistical Office (NSO). *UTs & NE States based on 2011 Census*

Indian States with Lowest Literacy Rate 2022:

As per the National Statistical Office (NSO) data for 2017-18 on state-wise literacy rate the country, Andhra Pradesh ranked Lowest in the list with 66.2% followed by Rajasthan & Bihar.

States with Lowest Literacy Rate

Sl. No	State	Male	Female	Average
1	Andhra Pradesh	73.4	59.5	66.4
2	Rajasthan	80.8	57.6	69.7
3	Bihar	79.7	60.5	70.9
4	Telangana	80.5	65.1	72.8
5	Uttar Pradesh	81.8	63.4	73
6	Madhya Pradesh	81.2	65.5	73.7
7	Jharkhand	83	64.7	74.3
8	Karnataka	83.4	70.5	77.2
9	Chhattisgarh	85.4	68.7	77.3
10	Jammu & Kashmir	85.7	68	77.3

*Source: survey by National Statistical Office (NSO). *UTs & NE States based on 2011 Census*

Literacy Rate Urban Vs Rural 2022:

In India, the literacy rate for people 7 years of age and over was at 77.7%. The literacy rate in rural areas was 73.5%, whereas it was 87.7% in urban areas..

Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4	Column5	Column6	Column7
	Rural	Rural	Rural	Urban	Urban	Urban
	Literacy	Literacy	Literacy	Literacy	Literacy	Literacy
States	Rate	Rate	Rate	Rate	Rate	Rate
States	Male	Female	Average	Male	Female	Average
Andhra Pradesh	67.5	53.4	60.4	86.3	73.1	79.6
Assam	89.4	79.9	84.9	96.1	91.4	93.8
Bihar	78.6	58.7	69.5	89.3	75.9	83.1
Chhattisgarh	84	65.6	75	91.8	82.3	87.2

Delhi				94.1	83.4	89.4
Gujarat	85.7	68	77	95.2	86.3	91.1
Haryana	85.8	66.4	77	92.5	81.2	87.3
Himachal Pradesh	92.3	79.2	85.6	97.8	93	95.5
Jammu & Kashmir	84.9	66	75.8	88.5	75.7	82.6
Jharkhand	80.6	61.4	71.4	92.6	78.6	86.1
Karnataka	78.2	63.1	71	92.5	83.7	88.3
Kerala	96.7	94.1	95.4	98.2	96.4	97.3
Madhya Pradesh	77.9	61	69.8	91.4	79.5	85.8
Maharashtra	87	71.4	79.4	95.3	87.6	91.7
Odisha	82	67.3	74.9	94.4	85.9	90.2
Punjab	85.5	74	80	93.8	86.7	90.5
Rajasthan	77.6	52.6	65.5	91.1	74.6	83.5
Tamil Nadu	84.2	70.8	77.5	92.3	85.9	89
Telangana	70.6	53.7	62.1	91.7	79	85.5
Uttarakhand	93.1	79	86.1	97.4	85.9	92
Uttar Pradesh	80.5	60.4	70.8	86.8	74.9	81.2
West Bengal	82	72.6	77.4	91.4	84.7	88.1
All-India	81.5	65	73.5	92.2	82.8	87.7

Source: survey by National Statistical Office (NSO)

Completed educational level of population for different age-groups 2022:

- Distribution of rural populations as a percentage (ages 15 years & above by highest completed levels of education)
- 31.5% of the population lacked literacy, 20.9% had literacy up to the primary level, 17.2% had upper primary/middle level literacy, 24.9% had secondary and higher secondary level literacy, and 5.7% had a degree or above.

Percentage distribution of urban residents/population(aged 15 years and above) according to greatest level of education attained:

- 13.9% of people did not have access to literacy, 14.7% had literacy up to the primary level, 14.0% had upper primary/middle level literacy, and 35.8% had secondary and higher level literacy.**21.7% were graduate& above.**

Source: survey by National Statistical Office (NSO)

FINDINGS:

1. Male literacy rate is higher than the female literacy rate in India 2022 according to NSO survey.
2. Kerala has the highest average literacy rate and Andhra Pradesh has the lowest average literacy rate in India 2022.
3. Urban literacy rate is more than the Rural literacy rate in India.

CONCLUSION:

A high literacy rate (or low illiteracy rate) indicates the presence of a primary education system and/or literacy programmes that have made it possible for a significant portion of the population to learn how to use the written word (and perform basic arithmetic calculations) in daily life and to continue learning. A literate person is a valuable asset to the prosperity of a country.

To ensure that people have the complex communication and critical thinking abilities required to succeed in the workplace and a global economy, a high literacy rate is crucial. Over the past 40 years, India's literacy rate has substantially increased. The National Survey of India's report estimates that India's literacy rate would be 77.7% in 2022. 73% of people in 2011 were literate. 4% more people now live there than according to the most recent census.

Although that is quite impressive in comparison to other emerging nations, it still means that almost one in four Indians cannot read or write (compared to about one in eight people worldwide). India's most literate state is Kerala. Kerala has a literacy rate of 96.2%. India will achieve universal literacy, according to UNESCO, in 2060.

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